

Psycho-Social Challenges for Children Education in Emergency Situation as Expressed by Secondary Teachers in Niger State: Implication for Counselling

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Abstract

The study examined psycho-social challenges for children education in emergency situation as expressed by secondary teachers in Niger State: implication for counselling. Access to education is a fundamental tool for child protection which inherently provides physical, psychosocial and cognitive protection. In appropriate security conditions, physical protection may be enhanced by the provision of adult supervision and a safe place to play. Psychosocial protection is offered through opportunities for self-expression, the expansion of social networks and access to structure and regular routines by placing children in the social role of learners. The population of the study consisted of all senior secondary school teachers in Chanchaga Local Government Area in Niger state. The target population consists of all the teachers in both public and private secondary schools in Chanchaga Local Government Area of Niger state. The sample for the study was 120 teachers randomly selected for the study. "Psycho- Social Challenges for Children Education in Emergency Situation questionnaire" (PSCCEESQ) was used. The study revealed that children in emergency situation are faced with myriad of challenges such as separation from family, deteriorating interpersonal and family relationship, loss of identity and child labour, challenges with attending school, loss of caregiver etc. Hence recommends adequate counselling for teachers and parents in the provision of psychosocial support.

Key words: Psycho-Social, Education, Emergency, Situation

Introduction

Education in emergencies saves lives. Conflict and disaster destroy normalcy and upend the lives of those affected especially in the case of children. Young people caught in emergency situations are thrown into unfamiliar and hostile realities, often without the safety nets they once

enjoyed such as school and family. The term “emergency education” is used at inter-agency level to refer to education in situations where children lack access to their national education systems, due to man-made crises or natural disasters.

According to Gordon (2018), Education in emergencies’ refers to the quality learning opportunities for all ages in situations of crisis, including early childhood development, primary, secondary, non-formal, technical, vocational, higher and adult education. Education in emergencies provides physical, psychosocial and cognitive protection that can sustain and save lives in emergency and protracted humanitarian contexts. Education in terms of this nature does not have particular features. Over recent years, awareness of the importance of education in emergencies has grown, and education is now included in international disaster relief funding appeals alongside other ‘traditional’ humanitarian sectors such as water and sanitation, health and shelter. Where teachers have been killed, injured, have fled, or are otherwise occupied with fighting or with their own survival and that of their families, ‘emergency teachers’ may need to be recruited from within the local population. Condensed, rapid training programmes for new, inexperienced teachers are a common feature of emergency education programmes. The programme content has to be adapted according to specific, local needs, but the protection and promotion of students’ psychosocial well-being underpins most interventions. In times of crisis, the restoration of formal and non-formal education programmes as early as possible is a significant step towards restoring normalcy and providing reassuring routine, continuity and hope for the future of both the children and their communities(UNESCO, 2008)

According to UNESCO (1999), educational emergency is a crisis situation created by conflicts or disasters which have destabilized, disorganized or destroyed the education system, and which require an integrated process of crisis and post-crisis response. Education in emergencies refers to a broad range of educational activities, formal and non-formal which are life-saving and life-sustaining and, therefore, critical for children, youth and their families in times of crisis. Crisis situations include natural disasters such as earthquakes, tsunamis and floods, as well as man-made conflicts. Emergency education programmes are designed according to the particular context of the environment and may be short-term, temporary solutions such as ‘tent schools’ for when school buildings are destroyed, damaged or inaccessible. However, education in emergencies also refers to longer-term education policy and programme development in chronic crisis situations. These include situations where refugees and internally displaced persons (IDPs) are uprooted for many years and have long-term education needs, or where the state is chronically ‘fragile’ and unable or unwilling to provide quality education services for the population. Education in emergencies covers education activities in post-emergency recovery, reconstruction and peace-building periods. Education activities evolve over time and generally span different phases of the crisis such as acute emergency, recovery and reconstruction.

According to Nwankwo and Otaru (2019), there are no clear dividing line exists between ‘emergency’ and ‘regular’ education, especially in chronic crisis and reconstruction contexts, and much accepted ‘good practice’ applies equally across both. They found out that a significant difference in the psycho-social impact and needs of children education in emergency situation in Nigeria as expressed by teacher in Federal Capital territory based on age and gender.

Quality, relevant education is a right of all children. Children in crisis situations often need new and different knowledge, skills and learning experiences in order to survive and to thrive in changed circumstances. They are particularly vulnerable, facing increased risks of physical, psychological and emotional harm. Quality educational initiatives employed at the outset of an emergency can mitigate these circumstances and provide much needed survival skills to understand the dangers of a new environment. These include initiatives to teach landmine awareness, living and surviving in refugee camps, basic health and hygiene information, how to protect oneself from sexual abuse, and the provision of psychological support (Price, 2011). Emergency education programmes often contain elements of disaster prevention, preparedness and mitigation, such as lessons for students about how to protect themselves in the event of an earthquake or what to do if rebel forces come to their village. In conflict-affected contexts, the inclusion of peace education and conflict resolution in education programmes for children and youth should support peace processes at different levels and contribute towards more peaceful futures. Education content to counter these risks may include, for example, land mine education, health and nutrition education, and other life skills such as HIV/AIDS prevention (Jackie, 2006).

Refugees or internally displaced children may need to learn in a different language than that of the local, host population and to follow a curriculum that will allow them to transfer back into the education system when they return home. However, for children and youth displaced over a long period, learning the language of the host community may be important for ensuring future income-generating possibilities, as well as for building bridges between communities.

Major emergencies of whatever nature (transport accident, flooding, insurgency, militancy, storm or fire) create a wide range of psychological and social challenges at individual, family, and community levels. These emergencies create acute short term impacts but also have the potential to undermine the long-term mental health and psychosocial well-being of affected populations. A significant priority in the psychosocial response to major emergency is to support and promote the resilience and resourcefulness of individuals and communities in a manner that helps to lessen the impact of the event (Ahmed, 2017).

Psycho-social well-being is based on an inseparable combination of biological, emotional, spiritual, cultural, social, mental, and material aspects of experience. Instead of focusing exclusively on the physical or psychological aspects of health and well-being, psycho-social programmes emphasis the totality of people's experience and underline the need to view these issues within the context of the wider family and community networks in which they occur (Inter-Agency Network for Education in Emergencies (INEE), 2016). A psychosocial approach to children and adult in emergencies moves away from focusing on individual clinically based diagnoses to focusing on holistic, broad-based preventative programmes that promote resilience and develop coping strategies across the entire affected group. This leads to improvements in general stress related symptoms among those with and without specific disorders, and can thereby significantly reduce the numbers of those that do require any specialist intervention. Psycho-social programmes are implemented through a complementary, integrated and multi-sectoral approach (Mattingly, 2017).

Statement of problems

Children (0-18 years of age) are a highly vulnerable segment of the population in times of disaster. Under normal conditions, there are components at the governmental, private and non-profit level which together form the networks on which children depend to support their development and protect them from harm. In addition to these systems, children fall under the supervision of their parents, guardians and/or primary caregivers. Once a disaster occurs, however, most or all of these foundations in a child's life may suddenly collapse. The child care centres and schools to which they were enrolled may be damaged, destroyed or used for shelters. Their parents or guardians may be stretched between caring for the needs of their children and addressing the needs of the whole family's recovery. The child victims, who are generally incapable of managing their own needs, can suffer disproportionately and may fall behind their peers in development and education.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to examine Psycho- Social Challenges for Children Education in Emergency Situation as Expressed by Secondary Teachers in Niger State: Implication for Counselling. It is expected that the results of the findings of this study will help parents, the communities, the school counsellors, administrators and teachers to recognize the psycho-social challenges learners undergo and how best to proffer solutions or possibly, adequate way of assisting the learner with psycho-social needs.

Research Question: What are the Psycho- Social Challenges for Children Education in Emergency Situation as expressed by secondary teachers in Niger State?

Research Hypotheses: Age and gender has no significant influence on the Psycho- Social Challenges for Children Education in Emergency Situation as expressed by secondary teachers in Niger State

Method

The research design adopted for this study is the descriptive survey method. Descriptive survey method was used to conduct the study since it enabled the researcher to gather information about the population of the study. The population of the study consisted of all senior secondary school teachers in chanchaga Local Government Area in Niger state. The target population consists of all the teachers in both public and private secondary schools in chanchaga Local Government Area of Niger state. Multistage sampling procedure was adopted for this study. The sample for the study was 120 teachers who were randomly selected from six purposively senior secondary schools in Chanchaga Local Government area namely; Army Day Secondary school, Minna; GidanKwano Secondary School, Minna; Galaxy International School, Minna; Hill Top Model Secondary School, Minna; Ideal Royal International school, Minna and Exceptional Victory International School, Minna. These schools were selected purposively because they are purely academics institutions. Random sampling was adopted to select respondents from these schools to give an

equal chance of being selected. The selection of one subject has no influence on the non-selection of the other.

The instrument used for collecting data for this study was titled “Psycho- Social Challenges for Children Education in Emergency Situation questionnaire” (PSCCEESQ). The questionnaire was developed by the researcher and the items were derived from the reviewed literature. The instrument has two parts (Section A & B). Section A consists of demographic information and Section B has 10 items. The responses were structured using 4-point Likert-type rating scale with the following grading: Strongly agree (SA) =4 points, Agree (A) =3 points, Disagree (D) = 2 point and Strongly Disagree (SD) =1 point. The mean score is 2.5 (4+3+2+1/4). This implies that for section B of the instrument, any mean score between 2.5 and above will be adjudged as Psycho-Social Challenges for Children Education in Emergency Situation as expressed by secondary teachers in Niger state and vice versa. To ascertain the validity of the instrument, it was given to experts in Educational Research Centre (ERC), Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council, (NERDC) Sheda- Abuja to vet. The experts made corrections and suggestions which were taken into consideration. The experts adjudged the instrument valid. To establish the reliability of the instrument, it was administered on a representative sample of (20) respondents twice at an interval of four weeks. The two set of scores were correlated using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Formula. A correlation coefficient of 0.79 was derived which shows that the instrument was reliable for the study. Descriptive statistics; percentage and mean score were used to analyze participants’ demographic data, research question and t-test hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level of significance.

Results

Research Question: What are the Psycho- Social Challenges for Children Education in Emergency Situation as expressed by secondary teachers in Niger State?

Table 1: Rank Order of Psycho- Social Challenges for Children Education in Emergency Situation as expressed by secondary teachers in Niger State

Item No.	As a teacher Psycho-Social challenges of children education in emergency situation are as:	Mean	Rank
1	Separation from family	5.29	1 st
3	Deteriorating interpersonal and family relationship	5.16	2 nd
2	Loss of identity and child labour	5.09	3 rd
5	Challenges with attending school	4.79	4 th
4	Loss of caregiver	4.48	5 th
8	High prevalence of sexual violence and early marriage	4.11	6 th
7	Right to participate in decision making	3.76	7 th
6	Thinking and worrying all the time	3.69	8 th
10	Withdrawal and isolation	3.57	9 th
9	Poor self-care, hygiene and nutrition	3.49	10 th

Table 2 shows the Psycho- Social Challenges for Children Education in Emergency Situation as expressed by secondary teachers in Niger state. Items 1 (Separation from family) ranked 1st with a mean score of 5.29; item 3(Deteriorating interpersonal and family relationship) ranked 2nd with a mean score of 5.16; item 2 (Loss of identity and child labour) ranked 3rd with a mean score of 5.09, item 5 (Challenges with attending school) ranked 4th with a mean score 4.79; item 4 (Loss of caregiver) ranked 5th with a mean score 4.48. From the forgoing and the responses of the respondents shows that from their experience and knowledge of the happenings in Niger state, learners are faces with series of psycho- social challenges as result of the incessant bandits and kidnapping activities in the state.

Hypothesis Testing: Age and gender has no significant influence on thePsycho- Social Challenges for Children Education in Emergency Situation as expressed by secondary teachers in Niger State

Table 2: t-value of Psycho- Social Challenges for Children Education in Emergency Situation as expressed by secondary teachers in Niger state based on age and gender

Variables	N	Mean	SD	Df	P-value
Age					
20-40	86	39.47	6.97	118	0.21
41-60	34	37.04	5.52		
Gender					
Male	51	37.07	5.76	118	0.13
Female	69	38.44	6.44		

Table 2 shows a p-value of 0.21 for age and 0.13 for gender at 0.05 level of significance. The p-value is greater than the alpha level at 0.05. The hypotheses were accepted. Hence, age and gender has no significant influence on the Psycho- Social Challenges for Children Education in Emergency Situation as expressed by secondary teachers in Niger State.

Discussion

Education and psychosocial support are purported to have a dynamic and mutually reinforcing relationship. The Education For All (EFA) Global Monitoring Report for 2011 (UNESCO 2011) focused on education in conflict settings and recognised the importance of psychosocial interventions in addressing the negative effects of conflict, including depression, trauma, shame and withdrawal, which can have significant consequences for individual learning. According to UNICEF (2009) effective child-centred learning is important in promoting the psychosocial wellbeing of both learners and teachers. Evidence shows that students' relationships with teachers are important predictors for academic performance and positive health and social behaviours. Several meta-studies identified perceptions of teacher fairness and teacher respect for students as important contributors to resilience and psychosocial wellbeing (Tol, 2013; World Bank, 2014; Noltemeyer & Bush, 2013; Joynes 2016).

To strengthen the efforts in promoting psychosocial support within educational programming in emergencies, UNICEF, Save the Children, International Rescue Committee, amongst others noted the importance teachers and school counselors knowledge and expertise in psychosocial intervention, hence, the nexus for this study.

The finding of this study reveals that there is no significance in the psychosocial challenges for children education in emergency situation on the basis of age and gender as expressed by secondary school teachers in Niger State. The study also revealed that children in emergency situation are faced with myriad of challenges such as separation from family, deteriorating interpersonal and family relationship, loss of identity and child labour, challenges with attending school, loss of caregiver, high prevalence of sexual violence and early marriage, right to participate in decision making, thinking and worrying all the time, withdrawal and isolation and poor self-care, hygiene and nutrition.

In support of the finding of the study, children in crisis situations often need new and different knowledge, skills and learning experiences in order to survive and to thrive in changed circumstances. They are particularly vulnerable, facing increased risks of physical and emotional harm hence the need for virile educational content to counter these risks such as land mine education, health and nutrition education, and other life skills such as HIV/AIDS prevention (Plan International, 2019).

In line with the findings of this study Kazeem (2015) opined that women and girls are vulnerable due to lack of dignity materials, insecurity, and lack of good toilet facilities. Women and girls are vulnerable due to far location of latrines in the site and other vital social amenities. Many IDPs expressed having undergone severe psychosocial distress in escaping violence and still being experienced throughout displacement.

In variance with the finding of this study Inter-agency Network for Education in Emergencies (INEE) (2020) gave an empirical overview of what works to support learning outcomes for girls in emergencies. The finding shows that girls in emergencies situation are disadvantaged at all stages of education and are more likely to be out-of-school than in non-emergency settings. In the same vein, girls are also struggling to learn, in fact, it is estimated that by 2030, one in five girls in crisis-affected countries will not be able to read a simple sentence.

In line with the finding of this study, numerous studies have documented that people of all ages are resilient in the face of adversities. Focusing on psychosocial needs and protective factors is an important long-term goal for positive mental health and psychological functioning of children in emergency situation. Protective factors for children include age, levels of self-esteem/efficacy, maintenance of cultural identity, social support from peers and family, a sense of belonging and safety in school and community, and innovative social care services (Masten & Narayan, 2012; Worthman, Plotsky, Schechter & Cummings, 2010; Tol, Song & Jordans, 2013; Marley & Mauki, 2018).

Psychosocial support services are greatly needed to help families deal with trauma and Social support often moderates depression among the internally displaced persons. When IDPs are

forced to flee their homes, often they escape with only the clothes on their backs. Women are usually the ones who must secure the family's necessities. The basic human needs are the fundamental right of all displaced persons and psycho-social needs. These include food, water, shelter, non-food items (blankets, clothes, pots, etc.), health care, sanitation facilities, education, and opportunities for income generation, empathy, unconditional positive regard, love and care (Tal, 2020).

Implication for counselling

The nature of emergency service work can involve regular exposure of personnel to traumatic incidents. This requires emergency service professionals to understand and to manage the post traumatic reactions of individuals with whom they are dealing. Equally their frequent exposure to traumatic incidents can render professionals themselves vulnerable to post traumatic stress reactions. For this reason, the specific emotional and psychological sequelae of traumatic experiences together with appropriate individual and organizational interventions are considered in more depth.

Following an emergency situation, people may develop Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD), which is psychological damage that can result from experiencing, witnessing, or participating in an overwhelmingly traumatic (frightening) event. Children with this disorder have repeated episodes in which they re-experience the traumatic event. Children often relive the trauma through repetitive play. In young children, distressing dreams of the traumatic event may change into nightmares of monsters, of rescuing others or of threats to self or others. PTSD rarely appears during the trauma itself. Though its symptoms can occur soon after the event, the disorder often surfaces several months or even years later. Counselling parents and teachers will help to identify some changes in children such as refusal to return to school and "clinging" behaviour, shadowing the mother or father around the house; Persistent fears related to the catastrophe (e.g., fears about being permanently separated from parents); Sleep disturbances such as nightmares, screaming during sleep and bed-wetting, persisting more than several days after the event; Loss of concentration and irritability; Behaviour problems, i.e., misbehaving in school or at home in ways that are not typical for the child; Physical complaints (stomachaches, headaches, dizziness) for which a physical cause cannot be found hence the need for counselling intervention of the rightful psychosocial needs of those in emergency situation.

It is important that counselling skills are practised in full knowledge of the individual and organizational responsibilities for their use. Thus the trained use of counselling skills by personnel in their various roles as professionals, peers and managers is discussed within a legal and professional perspective. The more detailed information on the ethical and legal implications in the use of counselling skills is by its nature bound by theory and can be used for reference when required.

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